

Semi-Structured Interview Guide

Working Title: Exploring the Adoption of MLOps Architectural Components Through the Lens of Sustainable Software Architecture

Introduction & Consent (5 min)

- Thank you for participating in our study
- We are interested in the adoption of MLOps in the context of digital transformation across different domains from the perspective of sustainable software architecture.
- This interview should take about 50~60 minutes
- Your responses will be kept confidential and will only be reported on in aggregate form
- Can I record the interview?

Introductory Questions (10 min, time box)

- Can you briefly describe your current role and involvement with ML systems?
- What kind of ML systems or pipelines have you worked on **in production**?

Key Questions (30 min)

Architectural design decisions

- Can you describe which MLOps components and tools you are currently using?
 - Can you give some examples of: Data curation, Version control, Pipelines/Scripting/Automation, Orchestration, Monitoring, Logging etc.
- Can you describe the decision process to adopt components and tools in your organization?
 - Who are the key stakeholders involved in the decision making?
 - What can you tell about prioritization and timing of adoption?
 - Which alternatives have been considered and why?
 - How do you document these decisions?
- Have you ever opted not to adopt a certain MLOps component and why?
 - How do you evaluate MLOps components for adoption?
 - What criteria have you used for this evaluation?
 - How do you weigh technical factors (performance, scalability) against non-technical factors (cost, vendor lock-in, community support)?

Economic Sustainability

- In what way does adoption MLOps components affect the cost of developing or maintaining your ML system?
 - Licensing, cloud usage, maintenance?
- Have you experienced long-term savings or hidden costs from MLOps adoption?
 - Did you consider ROI and TCO?

Technical Sustainability

- How does adoption MLOps components affect the maintainability and scalability of your ML systems?
 - Can you give an example?
 - Have you considered the vendors long term plans or roadmap?
- Has adoption of MLOps added complexity or technical debt?
 - Can you give an example?
 - Has MLOps made you ML system more modular?

Social Sustainability

- How does adoption MLOps components affect collaboration between different roles or teams within your organization?
 - Can you give an example?
- How does adoption of MLOps influence the explainability, compliance with regulations and involvement of stakeholders?
 - Can you give an example?

Environmental Sustainability

- How has the adoption of MLOps components affected your use of resources?
 - Compute, Storage, On-prem vs cloud, vs edge?
- How has adoption of MLOps components influenced you monitoring of resources?
 - What metrics do you track?
 - Do you specifically track energy usage or carbon emissions?

Supplementary Questions (10 min, only if time permits)

- Looking back at your MLOps journey so far, what would you have done differently and why when designing your ML architecture?
- Is there anything else you would like to share about your experience with MLOps and sustainability?